

EFFECT OF AI-INTEGRATED FLIPPED CLASSROOM INSTRUCTIONS ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN TRIGONOMETRY IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN YENAGOA.

BY

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of four AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions on students' academic performance in Trigonometry in Public Secondary Schools in Yenagoa. Three research questions guided the study and three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A quasi-experimental design using Pretest-Posttest non-equivalent control group type was adopted for the study. The population consisted of 5,563 Senior Secondary School one (SS1) students offering mathematics in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area. The sample size of 102 SS1 students was drawn from two public secondary schools using purposive sampling technique and were taught the Trigonometry topic. The numbers comprised 45 students in the experimental group taught using pre-recorded videos, and interactive modules in Edcafe, Khan academy, Edupuzzle, and Geogebra online AI-integrated flipped classroom platforms, while 57 students in the control group were taught using Direct Instructional method in the classroom. The instruments used for data collection were Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) and Reasoning Ability Test (RAT) developed by the researcher. It was validated by Three experts in mathematics education and test construction. Kuder-Richardson formula 20 (KR-20) was used to determine the reliability of the instruments and a reliability coefficient of 0.76 and 0.84 were obtained for MPT and RAT respectively. Adjusted mean was used for answering the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses. The findings showed that students taught trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions performed significantly better than those taught using the direct instruction method with large effect. The findings indicate a non-significant difference between the performance of male and female students taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions with negligible effect. It was also found that there is significant difference between the mean performance score of students with different ability taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions with large effect. It is therefore recommended that educators should adopt the AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions in Yenagoa by selecting appropriate AI-integrated flipped classroom platforms and tools that are suitable for learner's need in teaching mathematics to enhance students' academic performance in the subject.

Key words: AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions, Direct instruction method, mathematics academic performance, Trigonometry.

Introduction

Mathematics is an important subject that prepares learners with critical thinking, logical reasoning, and problem-solving skills vital for success in scientific, technological, and economic disciplines. It is one of the core subjects at the secondary school levels of education in Nigeria, as well as a pre-requisite subject for science and engineering base courses of study in tertiary institution of learning. However, it continues to be

perceived as difficult by many Nigerian students and this has led to low performance and negative attitudes towards the subject (Afolayan & Olayinka, 2023). Some variables contributing to students' poor performance in mathematics include teacher-centered teaching methods, lack of individualized support, limited integration of technology and students' inability to connect abstract concepts with real-life experiences. This reflects consistently in low mathematics grades

among students at the secondary school level of education in Nigeria.

Academic performance is viewed as the degree to which a student achieved educational goals set from the beginning of a learning process, which demonstrate the learner's mastery of core competencies, knowledge and skills within the scope and subject curriculum (York, Gibson, & Rankin, (2015)). In Nigeria, it has been stressed that the performance of students in mathematics is grossly below expectation at both external and internal examinations (Adetula, 2024). Various educational stakeholders including parents are concern due to the difficulty students face in trying to pass mathematics, considering the fact that the subject is a core requirement in several terminal examinations such as the Junior secondary examination which is needed to progress to senior secondary classes, and the need for students to have a credit pass in the subject at the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination to write the Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) popularly called JAMB in other to progress to any tertiary institution in the country. Considering the various efforts educational stockholders and policy makers have put in place for curriculum reforms and training programs, many mathematics teachers still rely heavily on the direct instruction method, which emphasizes rote memorization of conceptual understanding and this approach has failed to address the problem of mathematics failure in secondary schools in Yenagoa, particularly their inability to solve mathematics problems in a complex topic such as trigonometry that requires both spatial reasoning and critical thinking (Orhani, 2024). As a result, there is a pressing need for an innovative and interactive instructional pedagogy such as the AI-integrated flipped classroom instruction which can promote better understanding,

student engagement, and improve academic performance of students.

According to (York, Gibson, & Rankin, (2015)), there are indicators used to measure academic performance, and from early time, educators and researchers have put forward many of these indices which include standardized test scores or grades, and other academics outcomes such as conceptual knowledge, procedural fluency, strategic competence, competency-based assessment including critical thinking, adaptive reasoning, and problem-solving (Holmes, Bialik, & Fadel, (2019)). Though all of these indices obviously indicate how students have achieved study goals, however, in this research study we try to adopt and focus on achievement score in a standardized test, and reasoning ability as indicator of academic performance. This is because reasoning ability is a mathematics proficiency index that demonstrates a student capacity to think logically and justify answers (Ferreder, Mhrka, Ayele, Adugna, (2024)), thus, it will help to justify the level of scores obtained by the students in the performance test.

Flipped classroom instruction is one of the instructional pedagogies gaining traction in Nigerian educational system due to teachers and students access to online tools and learning. According to Altemueller and Lindquist, (2017), flipped classroom model is “a learner-centered approach that reverses the traditional teaching structure by delivering instructional content outside the classroom, typically through pre-recorded videos, textbooks, and other instructional materials. Flipped classroom had been proven to enhance academic performance, moreover, with AI-integration to the flipped classroom model, the AI provides added advantages to this pedagogical method by on-line interactive capability of the AI such as problem-solving tasks, discussions and application-based

tasks” for students to gain better understanding before coming to classroom learning (Jor, 2025; Solanki, 2025). Studies have demonstrated the interactive and supportive capability of AI-integrated flipped classroom tools in guiding and answering students question while learning (Jor, 2025), and educators achieve this by leveraging on integrating AI with flipped classroom learning platforms using chatbots to provide additional support in explaining grammar, generating content, and learning through question and answer by dialoguing with the AI chatbot (Ling & Jan, 2025). Thus, AI-based systems accommodate students with varying academic abilities – whether high, average, or low ability, by dynamically adjusting difficulty levels and providing scaffolded learning experiences (Zawacki-Richter, Marín, Bond, & Gouverneur, (2020)). This model of learning enhances classroom active learning, better engagement and problem solving when students come to face-to-face interaction with teacher, and collaboration with other students as they construct knowledge on their own (Khatoon, 2024; Sultan, 2018). In fact, Lo and Hew (2020), asserted that AI-integrated flipped classroom has been shown to reduce negative emotion towards mathematics, improve student motivation, reduce mathematics anxiety, and removed barrier to collaboration in the classroom.

To achieve AI powered flipped classroom learning in this study, we leverage on four existing flipped classroom online platforms already integrated with AI capability namely: Edcafe, Khan academy, and Edupuzzle and Geogebra. that enabled us to generated lesson plans, curated interactive contents and personalized instructional materials including videos, quizzes, problems and worksheet for students to study on their own based on their needs prior to classroom learning (Suwendu, 2024; López-Villanueva, et al., 2024). In addition, AI Intelligent Tutoring Systems

(ITS) function to grade assignments, providing immediate real-time assessment feedback during the pre-class learning, enabling students to receive individualized feedback and support.

The AI-integrated flipped classroom learning model is grounded in constructivist learning theory of Jean Piaget and lev Vygotsky. Jean Piaget's Cognitive Constructivism supports the idea that learners actively construct their own knowledge through personal experience instead of passively receiving information from the teacher (Piaget,1952), while Lev Vygotsky's Social Constructivism emphasizes the importance of social interaction, collaboration, and scaffolding in constructing knowledge (Vygotsky, 1978). Both theories underpinned Ai-integrated flipped classroom learning model as students first engage with instructional contents such as videos, textbooks, and other instructional materials that are created or curated by the teacher and sent to them for personal learning with real-time assessment and automated feedback at home before coming to the classroom (Tabor, 2025). When students come together with prior knowledge they can actively participate in the learning process and easily engage in peer discussions, group work, and collaborative problem solving in the classroom. The flipped classroom model aligns closely with constructivist principles as it shifts learning from passive reception to active exploration (Khatoon, 2024; Låg & Saele, 2019; Sultan, 2018). Thus, students learning trigonometry using this model can actively build conceptual understanding of the subject matter through personal experience, classroom interaction, peer collaboration, and teacher scaffolding process.

Empirically, researches had demonstrated that students in flipped learning and AI-supported classroom environment tend to have better learning outcome and academic performance

than those in direct instruction classroom due to increased motivation, self-efficacy, interest, timely feedback, and deeper conceptual understanding (Jor, 2025; Solanki, 2025; Su & Yang, 2022; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2020). A study that compared flipped learning with traditional learning, gamification, and independent online study carried out by Lo and Hew, indicated that flipped learning provided most benefit to students, increased positive emotions towards mathematics, and reduced negative emotions (Lo and Hew, 2020). More also, it has also been discovered that flipped learning strategy led to improved conceptual understanding and reduced mathematics anxiety among different categories of students, particularly in complex topics like calculus (O'Flaherty & Phillips, 2015). They attributed these outcomes to the active learning environment and increased time for collaborative problem-solving during classroom sessions.

Furthermore, gender differences in mathematics academic performance with technological use have been investigated. While some studies show that male students often outperform females in mathematics and are more confident with technology, others highlight that these gaps are closing up with increased access to digital tools and equitable instructional practices (OECD, 2021). A study by Zainuddin and Halili suggested that when flipped classroom learning was integrated with AI, it offered a neutral platform that reduced gender-based learning gaps by supporting individualized learning paths and minimizing classroom anxiety (Zainuddin & Halili, 2016). Jiang et al. also argued that in a self-paced study, both female and their male peers perform equally, though males tend to complete their activities faster in an AI inclusivity classroom (Jiang et al., 2024). Additionally, a study by Zainuddin (2020) also found out that both genders benefited equally from flipped classrooms when content

is customized and supported by AI-based tools that reduced the cognitive load among genders. The system's adaptability allows differentiated instruction, hence supporting inclusive mathematics education. On the contrary, a study by Chen et al. (2025), concluded that female significantly outperformed in grade than their male counterparts in an engineering course delivered through a flipped learning method. These findings suggest that while AI-integrated flipped learning model eliminate passive learning among gender, the level of engagement and performance may be influence by the design, thus, instructional materials and the kind of AI model integrated should be considered and tailored to students' needs to mitigate any gender difference that can ensue. All these reviewed literatures lack local knowledge on the implementation and effect of AI-integrated flipped classroom model that could encourage its adoption in the Yenagoa context hence the need to carry out this study.

Statement of the Problem

Mathematics remains one of the most challenging subjects for secondary school students. In Nigeria, the National Bureau of Statistics, analysis of WAEC results from 1999 to 2024 shows no significant increase in the performance of students in mathematics, but rather fluctuating patterns (Adetula, 2024; NBS, 2022). This trend in mathematics achievement indicates failure of the prevailing direct instructional pedagogy in solving the problem of lack of improvement in mathematics performance among secondary school students in Yenagoa. Thus, there is need for an alternative student-centered method of learning such as the AI-integrated flipped classroom model that is interactive, engaging with capability to improve students' performance in the subject in Yenagoa. Recent innovations in educational technology, specifically the integration of Artificial

Intelligence (AI) into instructional techniques position this method of learning as a promising alternative for enhancing mathematics instructions and therefore needs to be explored in the context of Yenagoa.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of AI-integrated flipped classroom instruction on students' academic performance in mathematics. Specifically, the aims of the study is to:

1. Determine the mean performance score of students taught trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom model and those taught using the direct instruction method.
2. Determine the mean performance score of male and female students taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions.
3. Determine the mean performance of students with different reasoning ability levels that were taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean performance score of students taught Trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom instruction and those taught using the direct instruction method?
2. What difference exist in the mean performance score of male and female students taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions?
3. What is the mean performance score of students with different reasoning ability that were taught Trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were raised to guide the study. They were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of students taught Trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions and those taught using the direct instruction method.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female students taught Trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of students with different ability levels that were taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions.

Research method

The study adopted a quasi-experimental design, precisely the pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group type. This design is suitable for this study as random assignment to groups is not possible (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). It allows for the comparison of learning outcomes between an experimental group taught Trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom instruction and a control group taught using the direct instruction method.

The population comprised all Senior Secondary School One (SSS1) students offering mathematics in public secondary schools in Yenagoa Local Government Area, during the 2024/2025 academic session. This comprises Forty-four (44) secondary schools with a total of five thousand, five hundred and sixty-three (5,563) senior secondary school one (SSS1) student (Source: Bayelsa Post-Primary Education Board, 2025).

The sample consisted of 102 SSS1 students selected from two public secondary schools. The selection was done using purposive sampling technique, based on the availability of ICT facilities in the school. Intact SSS1 class from each school were selected, the one with ICT facilities served as the experimental group (45 students), and the other as the

control group (57 students). The use of intact classes preserved the natural classroom setting and minimized the disruption of school schedule (Walser, 2014).

The instrument for data collection was researcher developed Mathematics Performance Test (MPT) and Reasoning Ability Test (RAT) based on the concept of Trigonometry that was taught. MPT consisted of two sections; section A was designed to obtain demographic information of participant, while section B consist of 25 multiple-choice items designed to obtain students' performance score in mathematics on concepts of trigonometry (angle of elevation and depression, sine and cosine rules, and their applications). The questions are standardized questions obtained from NECO and WAEC past questions on the topic. On the other hand, RAT also consisted of two sections; section A was used to obtain demographic information of the participants, while section B consisted of 25 items designed to obtain reasoning ability score of the students. The RAT instrument was designed in line with the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) Cognitive Domain Framework that assess learner's metacognition across the three TIMSS cognitive domains namely knowing, applying, and reasoning (Mullis, Martin, Foy, & Hooper, (2016).). The reasoning ability score of students obtained was used to categorized them as high (67th percentile and above, that is top 33%), average (34th to 66th percentile – that is middle 33%), and low level (33rd percentile and below – bottom 33%), using the Percentile Rank Method (Mullis et al., 2016). The use of Percentile Rank Method aligns with norm-referenced interpretation, and it is both theoretically and conceptually consistent with the goals of “large-scale educational assessment” like Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) and the TIMSS

(that is employed in this study to determine reasoning ability), which utilized percentile-based standards to categorize students into globally defined performance levels (OECD, 2019; Mullis et al., 2016).

The instruments were subjected to both content and face validation by three experts in mathematics education and test construction. They reviewed the questions and made necessary contributions which were reflected in the final draft of the research instrument to be used. The reliabilities of the instruments were determined using the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20), and reliability coefficient of 0.77 and 0.81 were obtained for MPT and RAT respectively.

Furthermore, we carefully planned and designed lesson plans and instructional materials for both groups, the experimental group was taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom, and the control group was taught with direct instructional method without prior knowledge of the topic. The lesson plan was designed to meet the national curriculum standard on the trigonometry topic, stating the objectives of the lesson, elucidating formulas, and how to use the formulas to solve related theoretical and practical mathematics problems. The instruments MPT and RAT were first administered to both groups (experimental and control) before the intervention, to obtain the pretest scores which serves as a baseline data.

In the pre-class stage for the experimental group, four AI-integrated flipped classroom platforms were employed namely, Edcafe, Khan Academy, Geogebra, and Edupuzzle to let the student have access to instructional materials and learn before coming to the classroom (Xia, 2023). During pre-class stage, we first used Edcafe and Khan Academy to generate a clear lesson plan for the students. Secondly, instructional resources – videos, summary notes, mathematical problems,

workbooks, and quizzes were created and/or curated and assigned or sent to students to learn within specified timeline from [Edcafe](#), [Khan Academy](#), [Geogebra](#), [EduPuzzle](#) platforms (Edcafe, 2026; Khan Academy, 2022; Geogebra, 2026; EduPuzzle, 2026). Students were communicated with details of how to access the instructional materials in the platforms which entails opening the web version, creating their accounts, and login in to access the curated instructional materials assigned to them. Thirdly, students learn with materials, solve problems and provided answers in the platform which are

automatically graded by the AI Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS). Fourthly, students received instant feedback on right and wrong answers, with the correct explanation of answers. In addition, where student needs more explanation on the step-by-step procedure of solving problems, they enter the questions in “Geogebra Math Solver” for detailed step-by-step explanation. These activities which are presented in table 1 below helped students in the experimental group to learn on their own and grasp deep contextual understanding of trigonometry before coming to the classroom

Table 1: Description of how students interacted with each of the platforms:

Topic	Tool	Student's Activity
Trigonometric (Lesson plan)	Edcafe, Khan Academy	Students read and understand lesson objectives, schedules, instructional materials to be use, and duration.
Introduction to trigonometric ratios- Sine, Cosine, Tangent with illustrative diagram	Khan Academy, EduPuzzle, Edcafe	Students watch the interactive video on trigonometric contents, take quiz and solve problems to ascertain their level of understanding of the topic, and get instant feedback.
Application of trigonometric ratios in solving problems in angle of elevation and depression.	Khan Academy, EduPuzzle, Edcafe	Students watched videos on the topic: angle of elevation and depression, answered solve multiple-choice and essay-type questions embedded in the video clip at each key moment.
Solving problems in right angle triangle involving trigonometric ratios	Geogebra Math Solver.	Students type difficult questions in the App to get step by step explanation of solution to the problems.

During the in-class learning stage, where the students that took the online lessons interacted in a face-to-face session with the teacher. The class sessions focused on collaborative problem-solving tasks, scaffolding, and interactive discussions based on students’ AI-performance data. The teacher recapped and clarified any misconception the students may

have had while learning. More also, group work using real world problems were solved. Mini lessons were also carried out for struggling students to deepen their understanding. During post-class stage, students were assigned follow up exercises based on area of struggle by each student as diagnosed by the AI-platform, and teacher.

Teacher review analytics, and provide feedback to students.

After intervention in both the experimental and control groups, the two instruments - MPT and RAT was administered again to participated students to obtain post-test data in order to assess their learning performance.

The pre-test and post-test data collected were recorded for both the experimental and control group. The performance score obtained based on student groups, gender, and reasoning ability level were coded and analyzed with SPSS version 27, using Adjusted Mean that account for any difference in pre-test score to

answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) using pre-test as covariate was used to test for the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results are presented in tables based on the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1:

What is the difference in the mean performance score of students taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions and those taught using the direct instruction method?

Table 2: Adjusted Mean performance scores of Students using Pre-test scores as covariate.

Method	N	Adjusted Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Error (SE)
AI-integrated Flipped Classroom instructions	45	58.75 ^a	1.77
Direct Instruction	57	47.80 ^a	1.51

^a Covariates (pre-test performance test scores) in the model are evaluated at 33.20

Results in table 2 shows that after controlling for the covariate, the adjusted mean performance scores of students taught trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions and direct instruction method are 58.75 and 47.80 respectively. From the result, it could be inferred that those taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions ($\bar{x} = 58.75$, SE = 1.77) had a higher mean performance score than those ?

taught using direct instruction ($\bar{x} = 47.80$, SE = 1.51), indicating a clear difference between the two methods.

Research Question 2

What difference exist in the mean performance score of gender (male and female) students taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions

Table 3: Adjusted Mean performance scores of Male and Female Students in AI-Integrated flipped Classroom using Pre-test scores as covariate.

Method	Gender	N	Adjusted Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Error (SE)
AI-integrated Flipped Classroom instructions	Male	25	59.58 ^a	1.84
	Female	20	57.92 ^a	1.62

^a Covariates (pre-test performance test scores) in the model are evaluated at 34.71

Results in table 3 shows that after controlling for the covariate, the adjusted mean performance scores of male and female students taught trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions and direct instruction method are 59.58 and 57.92 respectively. From the result, it could be inferred that male students in the AI-integrated flipped class had a slightly higher mean performance score ($\bar{x} = 59.58$, SE =

1.84) than the female students taught with the same AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions ($\bar{x} = 57.92$, SE = 1.62), indicating a little difference between the two genders.

Research Question 3

What is the mean performance score of students with different reasoning ability level that were taught Trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions?

Table 4: Adjusted Mean performance scores of Students in AI-Integrated flipped Classroom with different Reasoning Ability Level.

Method	Reasoning Ability level	N	Adjusted Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Error (SE)
AI-integrated Flipped Classroom instructions	High (67th percentile)	9	66.92 ^a	1.84
	Average (34 th to 66 th percentile)	25	59.28 ^a	1.53
	Low (below 33 rd percentile)	11	50.08 ^a	1.62

^a Covariates (pre-test performance test scores) in the model are evaluated at 33.20

Table 4 above shows the adjusted mean performance scores of students with different reasoning ability Level that were taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instruction models. After controlling for pre-test score (pre-test as covariates), the results reveal that top 33 percent of the students in the 67th percentile with high reasoning has adjusted mean performance score of 66.92 (SE = 1.84), while the middle 33 percent in the 34th to 66th percentile with average reasoning ability has 59.28 (SE = 1.53), and those with low reasoning ability level below 33rd percentile has 50.08 score (SE = 1.62). The results indicate that there is difference in

performance score between students with different reasoning ability levels, while those with the highest tend to score higher, those in the low ability level score the least.

Hypotheses Testing:

The hypotheses in the study were tested at .05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean performance score of students taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom models and those taught using the direct instruction method.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Performance Scores of Students.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig. Level P<.05	Partial Eta Squared (η^2_p) Value
Pre-test (Covariates)	1256.03	1	1256.03	58.12	.07	0.039
Method (Main Effects)	818.12	1	818.12	37.85	.00	0.375
Residual	2139.66	99	21.61			
Total	4213.81	102	41.72			

a. R Squared = .712 (Adjusted R Squared = .659)

* Partial Eta Squared (η^2_p) (Effect) interpretation: $0.01 \leq \eta^2_p < 0.06$ = small effect, $0.06 \leq \eta^2_p < 0.14$ = medium effect, $\eta^2_p \geq 0.14$ = large effect (Cohen, 1988).

The ANCOVA result in table 5 shows that the calculated p-value ($p = .001$) of the main effect of methods is less than 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is statistically significant difference between the adjusted mean performance scores of students taught Trigonometry using the AI-Integrated flipped classroom method and those taught using the direct instruction method, $F(1, 99) = 37.85$, $p < .00$, $\eta^2_p = .375$. Based on these results, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of students taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom models and

those taught using the direct instruction method is rejected. In addition, the partial eta squared value of .375 indicates a large effect size (Cohen, 1988; Mullis et al., 2016), suggesting that AI-integrated flipped classroom model of teaching accounts for approximately 38% of the variance in academic performance scores.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students (gender) taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions.

Table 6: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Performance Scores of Male and Female Students Taught using AI-integrated flipped Classroom instruction.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig. Level P<.05	Partial Eta Squared (η^2_p) Value
Pre-test (Covariates)	32.08	1	32.08	2.16	.20	0.039
Gender (Main Effects)	8.08	1	8.08	0.55	.07	0.051
Residual	623.08	42	14.84			
Total	663.24	45	15.07			

a. R Squared = .571 (Adjusted R Squared = .699)

* Partial Eta Squared (η^2_p) (Effect) interpretation: $0.01 \leq \eta^2_p < 0.06$ = small effect, $0.06 \leq \eta^2_p < 0.14$ = medium effect, $\eta^2_p \geq 0.14$ = large effect (Cohen, 1988).

The ANCOVA result in table 6 shows that the calculated p-value ($p < .07$) of the main effect

of gender is higher than 0.05 level of significance, indicating that there is no

statistically significant difference between the adjusted mean performance scores of male and female students taught Trigonometry using the AI-Integrated flipped classroom model, $F(1, 42) = 8.08, p = .07, \eta^2_p = .051$. Based on these results, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of male and female students taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom models is retained. In addition, the partial eta squared value of .051 indicates small effect size (Cohen, 1988; Mullis et al., 2016), suggesting that AI-integrated flipped classroom model

accounts for only approximately 5.1% of the variance in academic performance scores of genders. This insignificant small effect size confirms that AI-integrated flipped classroom model is not a practically significant predictor of academic performance in mathematics among male and female students.

H03: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students with different reasoning ability level that were taught Trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom model?

Table 7: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of performance scores of Students with different Reasoning Ability Level in AI-Integrated flipped Classroom.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig. Level P<.05	Partial Eta Squared (η^2_p) Value
Pre-test (Covariates)	4.34	1	4.34	.39	.54	0.039
Reasoning Ability Levels (Main Effects)	9.70	2	9.70	.87	.03	0.251
Residual	346.20	41	11.17			
Total	360.24	45	10.92			

a. R Squared = .547 (Adjusted R Squared = .469)

* Partial Eta Squared (η^2_p) (Effect) interpretation: $0.01 \leq \eta^2_p < 0.06$ = small effect, $0.06 \leq \eta^2_p < 0.14$ = medium effect, $\eta^2_p \geq 0.14$ = large effect (Cohen, 1988).

From the ANCOVA result in table 7, the calculated p-value ($p = .03$) of the reasoning ability levels is less than the significance level of .05. Thus, the main effect of reasoning ability levels (high, average, low) on performance scores of students taught using AI-Integrated flipped classroom model is statistically significant, $F(2, 41) = 0.87, p = .03, \eta^2_p = .251$. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students with different reasoning ability levels taught Trigonometry using AI-integrated flipped classroom model is rejected. Also, the partial

eta squared value of .251 indicates a large effect size (Cohen, 1988; Mullis et al., 2016), suggesting that reasoning ability level accounts for approximately 25.1% of the variance in mathematics performance scores. This large effect confirms that reasoning ability level of students strongly determines their academic performance in mathematics.

Discussion

The findings from the results of the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom model and those taught using the

direct instruction method indicated a significant difference. Students taught the concept of trigonometry with AI-integrated flipped classroom model performed significantly better than those taught using direct instruction. Additionally, the findings reveals that AI-integrated flipped classroom pedagogy has large positive effect on students' academic performance score which confirms that AI-integrated flipped classroom model is a strong and practically significant predictor of academic performance in mathematics. The findings could be attributed to AI-supported platforms adapting content to suit different learners' independent learning paces and styles, detecting misconceptions, and provide targeted remedial instruction at home, which is particularly valuable in mathematics where personal mastery of foundational concepts is crucial for progression. The findings are in line with that of Lo and Hew (2020), who found that students in flipped classrooms performed significantly better than those taught using direct instruction methods. The findings also align with those of Jor, 2025; Solanki, 2025; Su & Yang, 2022; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2020 who concluded that students taught with AI-supported flipped classroom model tend to have better learning outcome and academic performance due to increased motivation, self-efficacy, interest, timely feedback, and deeper conceptual understanding.

Secondly, the findings from the results on the difference between the mean performance score of male and female students taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions indicated a non-significant difference. Even though AI-integrated flipped classroom model had a slightly higher mean performance, the difference is not large enough to produce significant outcome in male and female students' academic performance. More also, the effect size of AI-integrated flipped classroom model was observed to be small suggesting a negligible

effect. These findings reveals that the academic performance in mathematics do not depends on gender when using the AI-integrated classroom model. The findings could be attributed to AI-supported platforms' ability to provide active learning environment to both male and female students, provides neutral platform that reduced gender-based learning gaps, supporting individualized learning paths and minimizing classroom anxiety. The finding is in line with that of Jiang et al. (2024); Zainuddin (2020); and Zainuddin and Halili, (2016), who found that both male and female students benefited equally from flipped classrooms when content is customized to reduce the gender differences. However, the finding is contrary to that of (Chen, Xu, Zhang, and Yu, (2025). who reported that female significantly outperformed their male counterparts in an engineering course delivered through a flipped learning method

Lastly, the results also reveal a significant difference in the mean performance scores of students with different reasoning ability levels (high, average, low) taught using AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions. Also, the partial eta squared value indicated a large effect suggesting that reasoning ability levels of students have significant effect on their performance scores. These findings shows that students' academic performance in mathematics largely depends on reasoning ability in the AI-integrated flipped classroom model. The findings justify the fact that all students do not have the same reasoning ability and learning styles, and that is why AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions is design to accommodate students with varying academic abilities (Jiang, McClure, Tatar, Bickel, Rosé, & Chao, (2024). The finding is in line with that of O'Flaherty and Phillips (2015), who found that flipped classrooms led to improved conceptual understanding and reduced mathematics anxiety among different

categories of students. specifically in complex topics such as trigonometry and calculus.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed that students taught Trigonometry using the AI-integrated flipped classroom achieved better academic performance score compared to those taught using the direct instruction method, and that AI-integrated flipped classroom model significantly affect students' performance in mathematics in Yenagoa. Secondly, the effect of gender on students' academic performance score is negligible and both male and female students benefitted equally from the AI-integrated flipped classroom model in the region. Lastly, reasoning ability levels of students significantly affect their performance score when exposed to the AI-integrated flipped classroom pedagogy. Overall, students' academic performance in mathematics, depends on the AI-integrated flipped classroom model itself, and the level of their reasoning ability, but not on whether student is a male or female. This is attributed to the fact that the AI-integrated flipped classroom model makes students to become active learners, develop greater autonomy, increase motivation in learning mathematics, reduce mathematics anxiety, reduce gender gaps in mathematics studies, and improved students' preparedness for class activities.

Recommendation:

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were given:

1. Schools should integrate the AI-integrated flipped classroom instructions into mathematics learning, especially for teaching mathematics.
2. Teachers should undergo regular professional training to equip themselves with the skills needed to effectively implement AI-integrated flipped classroom pedagogies to maximize students' abilities and engagement.

3. Educational stakeholders should invest in developing AI tools tailored specifically for mathematics curriculum at the secondary school level,

References

- Adetula, O. A. (2024). Analysis of WASSCE Results from 2020-2024. *In uLesson blog*. <https://ulesson.com/blog/analysis-of-wassce-results-from-2020-2024/>.
- Afolayan, O.A., & Olayinka, J. (2023). Factors Influencing the Attitudes of Secondary School Students Towards the Study of Mathematics. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.168897269.95770924/v1>.
- Altemueller, L., & Lindquist, C. (2017). Flipped classroom instruction for inclusive learning. *British Journal of Special Education*, 44(3), 341–358. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8578.12177>.
- Bayelsa State Education Board (2024). Annual report on secondary school enrolment and performance. Yenagoa Bayelsa State Ministry of Education.
- Chen, X., Xu, M., Zhang, H., and W. Yu, (2025). Transforming IP Design Education with AI: A Comparative Study of AI-Integrated and Traditional Flipped Learning Models. doi: 10.1109/cste64638.2025.11092234.
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2nd ed.) Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Creswell, J. W. & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approach* (5th ed.) SAGE Publication.
- Edcafe, (2026). Edcafe AI – Brew Teaching Materials with AI. (<https://www.edcafe.ai/>).
- Edupuzzle, (2026). Edpuzzle (<https://edpuzzle.com>).
- Fererde, A., Mihrka, A. A., Ayele, M.A., Adugna, A. (2024). Enhancing Students' Conceptual Understanding and Problem-Solving Skill in Learning Trigonometry through contextual-based mathematical

- modelling instruction. *International Journal of Secondary Education*. 12(4). 108-149.
- Geogebra, 2026;). GeoGebra - the world's favorite, free math tools used by over 100 million students and teachers. (<https://www.geogebra.org>).
- Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). *Artificial Intelligence in Education: Promises and Implications for Teaching and Learning*. Centre for Curriculum Redesign.
- Jiang, S., McClure, J., Tatar, C., Bickel, F., Rosé, C.P., & Chao, J., (2024). "Towards inclusivity in AI: A comparative study of cognitive engagement between marginalized female students and peers," *British Journal of Educational Technology*, doi:10.1111/bjet.13467.
- Jor, J. (2025). Impact of artificial intelligence on engagement, motivation, work efficiency, and academic outcomes. 511–515. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003591511-79>.
- Khan Academy. (2022). Personalized learning through mastery. <https://www.khanacademy.org>.
- Khatoon, S. (2024). Flipped Learning: A Paradigm Shift in Education. *International Journal of Emerging Knowledge Studies*, 03(11), 916–922. <https://doi.org/10.70333/ijeks-03-11-010>.
- Låg, T., & Saele, R. G. (2019). Does the flipped classroom improve student learning and satisfaction? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *AERA Open*, 5(3), 23328584198703489. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23328584198703489>.
- Ling, Y., & Jan, J. M. (2025). Voices from the Flip: Teacher Perspectives on Integrating AI Chatbots in Flipped English Classrooms. *Education Sciences*, 15(9), 1219. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15091219>.
- Lo, C. K., & Hew, K. F. (2020). A Comparison of Flipped Learning with Gamification, Traditional Learning, and Online Independent Study: The Effects on Students' Mathematics Achievement and Cognitive Engagement. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 28, 464-481. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2018.1541910>.
- López-Villanueva, D., Campión, R. S., & Palau, R. (2024). Flipped Learning and Artificial Intelligence. *Electronics*, (17), 3424. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics13173424>.
- Mullis, I. V. S., Martin, M. O., Foy, P., & Hooper, M. (2016). *TIMSS 2015 international results in mathematics*. TIMSS & PIRLS International Study Center, Boston College.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), (2022). Report on WAEC Results Statistics from 2019 – 2021, 1-21.
- OECD. (2019). PISA 2018 results (Volume D): What students know and can do. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5f07c754-en>.
- O'Flaherty, J., & Phillips, C. (2015). The use of flipped classrooms in higher education: A scoping review. *Internet and Higher Education*, 25, 85–95.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), (2021). 21st-Century Readers: *Developing Literacy Skills in a Digital World*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/a83d84cb-en>.
- Orhani, S. (2024). Addressing Students' Challenges In Acquiring Trigonometric Function Concepts: Approach To Education for Sustainable Development. *Journal of Education For Sustainable Development Studies*., 1(2), 160-172 <https://doi.org/10.70323/jesds.v1i2.15>.
- Piaget, J. (1952). *The Origins of Intelligence in Children*. New York: International Universities Press.
- Solanki, T., (2025). Transforming Traditional Teaching Practices to Integrating AI with Pedagogical Innovations for Enhanced Learning Outcomes in Schools. *International Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*, 7(4). <https://doi.org/10.36948/ijfmr.2025.v07i04.53258>.

- Su, C. Y., & Yang, C. H. (2022). Artificial intelligence-enhanced flipped learning: Predicting students' learning satisfaction and engagement using machine learning algorithms. *Computers & Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 3, 100066. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2022.100066>.
- Sultan, A. S. (2018). The Flipped Classroom: An active teaching and learning strategy for making the sessions more interactive and challenging. *J. of Pakistan Medical Association*, 68(4), 630–632. https://ecommons.aku.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1023&context=pakistan_fhs_mc_ded.
- Suwendu, R. S. D. (2024). AI-Driven Flipped Classroom: Revolutionizing Education Through Digital Pedagogy. *British Journal of Education, Learning and Development Psychology*, 7(2), 169–179. <https://doi.org/10.52589/bjeldp-ltdjflih>.
- Tabor, J. (2025). Cognitivism, Constructivism, and the Classroom. *Advances in Computational Intelligence and Robotics Book Series*, 211–240. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3373-6007-2.ch007>.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Harvard University Press.
- Walser, T. M (2014). Quasi experimental in school: the case for historical cohort control groups, *Practical Assessment Research and Evaluation*. 19(6) 89- 95. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7275/17hj-1k58>.
- Xia, X. (2023). *Exploration and Practice of Flipped Classroom Model in Education Research Methods Course Based on Blended Learning*. Preceding Article, 243–247. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ccat59108.2023.00052>.
- York, T. T., Gibson, C., & Rankin, S. (2015). Defining and measuring academic success. *Practical Assessment, Research & Evaluation*, 20(5), 1–20.
- Zainuddin, Z. (2020). Flipped classroom instruction in mathematics: A gender-based analysis. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 15(12), 56–67.
- Zainuddin, Z., & Halili, S. H. (2016). Flipped classroom research and trends from different fields of study. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 17(3), 313–340.
- Zawacki-Richter, O., Marín, V. I., Bond, M., & Gouverneur, F. (2020). Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education – where are the educators? *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 17(1), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-020-00200-8>.

